

Opening the Future

How to Implement an Equitable Revenue Model for Open Access Monographs

Martin Paul Eve

Frances Pinter

Emily Poznanski

Tom Grady

DOI [10.5281/zenodo.7003979](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7003979)

Version 3 - updated Aug 2022 to incorporate minor clarifications

a project
funded by

Research
England

ARCADIA
A CHARITABLE FUND OF
LISBET RAUSING & PETER BALDWIN

Opening the Future: How to Implement an Equitable Revenue Model for Open Access Monographs

Martin Paul Eve

Frances Pinter

Emily Poznanski

Tom Grady

DOI [10.5281/zenodo.7003979](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7003979)

Version 3 - updated Aug 2022 to incorporate minor clarifications

Table of Contents

Introduction and Background Context.....	3
About the COPIM Project.....	4
What is Opening the Future?.....	4
What Opening the Future is Not	5
Assumptions.....	5
Why are Presses Interested in Opening the Future?.....	6
Financial Modelling and Scenario Planning.....	8
The Membership Modeller.....	8
Realistic Modelling	10
Tax Implications.....	11
Organizational Partnerships	12
Billing and Sales Partnerships.....	12
Jisc Collections.....	12
Knowledge Unlatched	12
LYRASIS.....	12
Open Book Collective	13
Delivery Partnerships	13
OAPEN.....	13
Project MUSE.....	13
Thoth.....	14
Marketing and Outreach.....	15
Outreach to Backlist Authors	15
Sample Email to Author	15
Sample Template Email to Library from Author.....	16
Outreach to Frontlist Authors.....	16
Outreach to Open Access or Scholarly Communications Librarians.....	17
Outreach to Acquisitions/Collection Librarians and Using Worldcat Data.....	17
Outreach to Library Consortia.....	18
Press Releases about New Signups	18
Conferences and Events	19
Signup Workflow	21
Process Diagram.....	21
Actors and Actions	22
Delivery of Subscription Content	22
Fixed Packages Should Not Change	23
Licensing: Use SERU Where Possible.....	23
Digital Preservation and Perpetual Access.....	24
Delivery of OA Content.....	24
Selection Procedures and Timescale	24
Technical Infrastructures.....	25
‘Signup’ Infrastructure	26
Open Book Collective	26
Appendix A: Jisc Collections Licensing Template	27
Appendix B: Financial Modelling Spreadsheet	28
Appendix C: Frequently Asked Questions.....	29
Bibliography.....	34

Introduction and Background Context

Covid-19 has thrown many aspects of university research culture into acute relief. As the reality of the virus dawned and campuses worldwide went into lockdown, publishers scrambled to unpaywall their research. Publishers made topical works and more general material openly available, through their own sites and platforms such as Project Muse and JSTOR. Physical collections became inaccessible and demand for openly accessible research skyrocketed. It is unclear that it is desirable to return to the previous systems of scholarly communication in the book publishing world, in which physical copies may remain affordable, even while e-licensing agreements for libraries are not.

This has been recognised in several recent global policy announcements including the cOAlition S/Plan S guidelines, and the recent UKRI consultation on OA. The latter's proposed measures include the possibility of zero-embargo green OA, more liberal open licensing, and the long-vaunted requirement for funded monographs to be in scope. This last element built on a longstanding policy history in the UK foreshadowing a mandate for OA monographs.

That said, the path to OA monographs is not free of obstacles. Among the many issues, the most frequently raised is the business model of Book Processing Charges (BPCs) and their apparent unaffordability, mostly due to distributional allocation of library resources. Happily, several recent reports have detailed non-BPC OA revenue and business models that presses could use to transition to OA - one of the most recent being COPIM's Revenue models for Open Access monographs 2020.¹ That report describes a variation on the journal 'Subscribe to Open' model whereby members 'subscribe to a backlist, with the revenue then used to make the frontlist openly accessible'. This constitutes a new business model for OA monographs that had not previously been implemented. We implemented this model, dubbed 'Opening the Future,' in a partnership between the COPIM project, the Central European University Press (CEUP), and Liverpool University Press (LUP). This model presents a potential route for the mass and sustainable transition to OA of many small-to-mid sized university presses.

This document sets out how we implemented this model, including the documentation of challenges, resources, timetables, and activities. It is intended as a roadmap for other presses that wish to implement an 'Opening the Future'-esque model. Of course, this document is unlikely to cover everything, but the authors are happy to respond to individual queries where this will prove helpful.

1 Izabella Penier, Martin Paul Eve, and Tom Grady, 'Revenue Models for Open Access Monographs 2020', *Community-Led Open Publication Infrastructures for Monographs*, 2020 <<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4011836>>.

About the COPIM Project

COPIM (Community-led Open Publication Infrastructures for Monographs) is an international partnership of researchers, universities, librarians, open access book publishers and infrastructure providers. It is building community-owned, open systems and infrastructures to enable OA book publishing to flourish.

COPIM is developing a significantly enriched not-for-profit and open source ecosystem for OA book publishing that supports and sustains a diversity of publishing initiatives and models, in the UK and internationally. To achieve its aims, the project is divided into seven work packages ranging from the technical (building open-source, community-based infrastructures that support the publication and dissemination of OA books), through to advocacy and knowledge sharing activities (establishing and consolidating partnerships between HE institutions and OA book publishers).

Work Package 3 (WP3) of COPIM is dedicated to knowledge exchange and transfer, as part of the project's central commitment to dissemination. It builds pathways to impact with relevant stakeholders from across the sector, including publishers ((New) University Presses, library-presses, scholar-led presses), academics, learned societies, and open technology developers. As part of its activities, WP3 is working to transition the business models of two university presses: the Central European University Press and Liverpool University Press.

What is Opening the Future?

Opening the Future is a revenue model for open access monographs in which a press solicits a relatively small financial contribution from a moderate number of academic libraries, in order to cover the costs of new OA publications. In return, the member libraries receive special access to elements of the press's backlist, as well as frontlist titles that are made OA. Libraries will retain access to the backlist for as long as they are members and with the option for the press to offer perpetual access to libraries after a certain period of membership. Membership will last a minimum of three years, with the option to renew after that. The revenue from the membership – that grants access to the backlist – will be used to fund the frontlist to be OA.

The aim of this approach is to continue to yield a sustainable source of revenue for a press while achieving the desired commitment to making more titles OA. Given the current global library environment and already existing budget pressures that have now been exacerbated by Covid-19, a consortial model of funding promises a cost-effective solution for OA that means no single institution bears a disproportionate burden. The model also yields an elastic approach to open access that can grow with the success of the model.

What Opening the Future is Not

Opening the Future is not like a ‘transformative agreement’ in the journal world. There is no linkage between an institution supporting the model and their own authors being allowed to publish OA. Opening the Future, as a result, is trying to break the link between institutions paying and their own authors being allowed to publish openly, in favour of the press securing a 100% open frontlist and so achieving the former by default. Opening the Future is better thought of as an attempt to build a one-time, open, global ‘collection’ that is shared by libraries in common, around the world.

Assumptions

There are several assumptions behind this model that make it possible and that show the aspirations for scaling:

- The target output volume is 25 new OA titles per year for a press-level conversion. For a series-level conversion, we are aiming for 4-5 titles.
- The model can work at the level of converting the entire press or on a single series.
- It costs between approximately €6,500 to €8,900 to produce the ‘first copy’ of each new title.
- The press can define and curate an attractive collection of backlist titles to offer exclusively to members.
- Library members will be banded according to their size - meaning their payments will be tiered high, medium, and low.
- Titles will be made OA only as and when enough members join and scaling is elastic – they would not be published upfront first and retrospectively funded.
- Membership will last a minimum of three years, with the option to renew for another three – access to the backlist is granted in perpetuity, after three years of membership or an upfront payment of three years’ worth.
- Membership will initially build over a three-year period, achieving the target revenue at end of year three. The number of OA titles will grow commensurately and gradually as more membership revenue allows more titles to be funded and published.
- There will be some flexibility around which books a library subscribes to each year.

This model has a number of characteristics in its favour, including pleasing library economics. For example, if an annual membership of €812 gives access to 50 backlist titles, and funds a further 25 OA per year - with only 200 member libraries joining this equates to around €15 per library, per title. The backlist/frontlist combination also provides a unique dual-route to rationalisation for acquisition librarians. Many institutions do not have dedicated OA funds, particularly for monographs: the fact that the backlist remains a subscription means that these libraries are able to

justify the expenditure as a purchase of books to which they would otherwise not have access. At the same time, every year of membership will grow their (open) collection by (in this instance) 25 titles. And those libraries with OA budgets are able to justify this expenditure because the new frontlist titles are openly accessible. This will also allow institutions that have access to block grants for OA to use this pot to fund the purchase. It is further possible for funders directly to support such consortial membership schemes.

Two of the major advantages of this model are, first, that the number of OA titles can grow (or contract) elastically with the revenue stream, and, second, that once the target volume is reached, membership/subscription prices can decrease in future years.

Pricing will, of course, be specific to the press that implements the model, but for CEUP we proposed three membership tiers with the highest band paying €1,200, the middle band at €800, and the lowest at €350. This pricing should be within the affordability of many academic libraries worldwide. We have modelled financial scenarios towards a target membership of 270 libraries, including slow and steady projections, enthusiastic ‘early adopter’ subscriptions, and even cancellations. While this last is not ideal for takeup of OA, it demonstrates a model that will allow flexibility: if the revenue is not in place, or if institutions cancel, then the volume of OA simply decreases.

Why are Presses Interested in Opening the Future?

“ The benefits of open access for books are clear. In the spring of 2020, when CEU Press made its titles freely available on Project MUSE: the usage figures soared, 7 out of the 10 most downloaded books were over ten years old, and the most downloaded title in China was called Academic Freedom. As a case study, this clearly demonstrated the need to find a sustainable route to open access for books, in general, and for the Press in line with its mission.

At the core, CEU Press aims to export to the rest of the world a body of knowledge that offers a path to a proper understanding of the region and the lessons learned that are of global relevance. Moreover, for us publishing is no longer simply about just producing content, but also about creating equitable opportunities for authors to make their research discoverable and accessible through open access and to create impact and engagement.

We wanted to find a model that: 1) provided sustainable funding for publishing OA books; 2) allowed for a gradual transition to OA as we did not have a subsidy to support the change and; 3) did not charge authors Book Processing Charges (BPCs) to publish as most of our authors (like so many other HSS scholars) do not have access to funds to cover OA publishing costs.

The Opening the Future (OtF) model allows for a gradual transformation in line with the pace of change in the library community, which minimises the risk a press might have to take. So as we increase our funding through this model, we can publish an increasing number of titles in OA. But its not an all or nothing approach.

For the press, the challenges lie around the resources needed to launch a new business model and to manage three streams concurrently: print, online and open access, each of

which requires different know how and different workflows. This has an inherent level of complexity, which we hope we will reduce over time, for publishers as well as librarians.”

– Emily Poznanski, Central European University Press

“ University presses exist to disseminate scholarship. A majority of university presses have long-standing programmes rooted in the humanities, disciplines for which the monograph remains a significant vehicle both to conceptualise research and to share it. Repeated narratives of the decline of the monograph ignore the strength of supply, with an unending pipeline of authors driven by a compelling mixture of intellectual hunger and career necessity. They ignore a growing potential audience, as the drive for impact has created ever more urgent and engaging long-form research outputs. The problem, of course, is the model. Open access has for some years served to unite authors with wider potential readership for journals but it has not been systematically adopted for books because of the substantial costs arising from length, complexity and curation. Faced with the possibility of a well-funded, openly available STEM and a closed-access, narrowly available HSS, scholarly book publishers should be willing to explore new models that maximise the audience for the monograph.

Opening the Future, with its realistic acknowledgement of publisher costs and of the realities of library budgets and policies, offers a potentially sustainable model to reform the dissemination of scholarly books. Liverpool University Press is ideally placed to test that assumption, as a mission-based publisher operating entirely without subsidy or endowment. If we can make the model work without a financial safety net then it should be possible for any publisher to make it work. To test the hypothesis behind OtF we have opted to work at series/discipline level. This has two advantages: first, it enables us to leverage an existing strength of the Press in the Modern Languages. We know who to market to, while librarians know that the LUP imprimatur is a guarantee of quality. OA may in time also serve as an editorial differentiator for prospective authors in our chosen field. Secondly, working at series level allows for more rapid progress than expensive larger collections but also avoids the inefficiency of title-by-title OA. Funding levels for a series OtF are comfortably within library means, while for publishers it is a minor risk but a major opportunity, with the option to scale up if the model gains traction.”

– Anthony Cond, Liverpool University Press

Financial Modelling and Scenario Planning

The Membership Modeller

The first step towards implementing an Opening the Future model is understanding your own press's finances and what the transformation will look like. To that end, we have produced a membership modelling tool that will allow you to insert your own figures and then to model the resulting scenarios (see Appendix B). In the tool, boxes in *yellow* should be replaced with your own figures (and you should only type in the boxes that are highlighted in yellow). Boxes in green represent automatically calculated incoming finances while boxes in red represent calculated outgoings.

Table 1: Description of variables in the spreadsheet modeller 'Variables' tab

Variable Name	Description	Default
Base cost per book	The basic cost per book that the press needs to recover.	€7,500.00
Approx. billing agent fee per membership transaction (presses may wish to add a slightly higher figure in this box to also account for sales agent fees, if applicable)	The fee requested by a billing agent per membership transaction.	€85.00
Bank fee per transaction	The fee requested by the Press's bank per transaction	€15.00
Higher Band	The fee rate for 'large' band (biggest) library subscribers.	€1,200.00
Middle Band	The fee rate for 'middle' band (middle size) library subscribers.	€800.00
Lower Band	The fee rate for 'lower' band (smallest) library subscribers.	€350.00
Number of titles in backlist	The number of titles that are offered in the 'backlist' package (i.e. how many books does the library get as an exclusive reward for joining?)	50
Number of yearly titles in frontlist	The number of titles that the press aspires to make openly accessible every year under this scheme.	25
OA deposit fee per book (e.g. OAPEN per-title fee)	The fee to deposit each OA book (for example, in OAPEN).	€10.00
OA deposit annual membership fee (e.g. OAPEN annual membership fee)	The annual membership fee to be able to deposit books (for example, the OAPEN annual	€175.00

Variable Name	Description	Default
	fee).	
Secondary annual OA deposit location fee (e.g. JSTOR)	The annual membership fee to be able to deposit books in a secondary location (for example, JSTOR).	€100.00
One-time setup fee	The one-off staff labour cost of sorting out the backlist titles into packages.	€2,000.00
Approx. annual fee (based on 300 members)	The annual fee from a platform provider to provide access to the backlist.	€3,000.00
Approx. annual deposit fee per backlist title	The annual fee per backlist title book for a platform provider, to provide access to the title.	€100.00
Creation of metadata records per backlist title	The cost of creating metadata records for an item of backlist content.	€50.00
Format-shift costs (e.g. improved digital copies, OCRing PDF text, creating epub) per title	The costs of ensuring that the backlist is in a viable format for digital delivery.	€100.00

Other tabs/sheets in the modeller also have configurable variables. For instance, the ‘Linear Data’ sheet describes what happens when members join at a rate of 84 per year, spread exactly evenly between the different banding levels. As a note: our experience with the Central European University Press and Liverpool University Press is that most memberships have originated from larger institutions, despite our attempt at fair pricing at the lower end.

This sheet also allows you to enter the number of Book Processing Charges that are anticipated to be secured, independently, and so will not count towards the Opening the Future scheme (but will nonetheless enable OA).

Different tabs/sheets depict different scenarios. For instance, the ‘Early Adopters’ sheets are designed to show a rapid uptake, followed by a longer tail.

Each sheet shows the projections for revenue and the number of funded books in each year at this stage. However, the safety and beauty of the scheme is that, if any of these figures are not met, the book should simply be processed as a ‘sales-only’/‘toll-access’ title. The model does not require a press to make a book openly accessible until the revenue target to enable this has been met.

When modelling costs, the crucial balance to strike is between value for money on the backlist and value for money on the OA frontlist. A good pricing level will yield a valuable return to libraries solely on the backlist (i.e. it will appear good value if they *only* received the backlist titles), solely on the frontlist (i.e. it will appear good value if they *only* received the OA frontlist titles), *and* it will appear very good value when the frontlist and backlist titles are combined.

Realistic Modelling

There are many factors that will affect the accuracy provided by the financial modelling tool. The rate of growth, for instance, will be dependent on the success of the marketing strategy and the level of resource that is devoted to these activities. It is always better to plan for more conservative growth and then to exceed this target than to make unrealistic predictions.

Our initial implementation of Opening the Future also took place against a number of significant world events and policy decisions that changed the landscape beneath our feet. First, the Covid-19 pandemic hit with associated fears for university library budgets. This caused a certain reticence among libraries amid budgetary constraint. Second, though, a number of policy announcements (such as the UKRI review) fuelled further OA book mandates. These look set to continue, with the review of the REF taking place in the UK. The US situation looks set never to be one of all-encompassing mandates, but it is true that various initiatives – such as Plan S – will steadily have influential knock-on effects.

Understanding the types of institution who are willing to join an initiative is also important. In the first year of CEUP's Opening the Future scheme, the Press achieved 41 signups across five packages (Figure 1). This amounted to £35,350 of OA funding or enough for five open-access monographs. Notably, all but one of the USA institutions was in the highest tier of subscriber fees. A similar pattern emerged for European libraries and almost all UK participants fell in the medium to high tiers. In the 6 month period beginning January 2022, CEUP's membership increased by another 30 libraries, thereby accruing funding for further OA titles to be published.

Figure 1: CEUP signups from January to December 2021

While CEUP's progress gives the best indicator that we have of signup rates, it is difficult to extrapolate from these data for a number of reasons:

- This was the first year of operation, meaning that much of our time was spent explaining the model, asking librarians to understand the premises, and generally spreading the word;
- We were operating during perhaps the most exceptional set of conditions in our lifetimes: the Covid-19 pandemic, with knock-on effects on library budgets;
- Library budgetary planning takes a long time to go through – once a library has decided that it wishes to participate, it can take up to 12 months for the funding to be approved and to become available for expenditure;
- Mandates for OA monographs are only now coming to prominence, with UKRI announcing their conditions mid-way through the year.

Possible results from these data include:

- Future signups will occur faster than in this first year because the model is better understood;
- Future signups will occur faster than in this first year because mandates place more pressure on institutions to support OA monographs;
- Future signups will occur more slowly than in this first year because library budgets are under increasing pressure, including from transformative agreements in the journal space;
- Future signups will occur more slowly than in this first year because a proliferation of models dilutes library resources.

Presses should, therefore, appraise their own brand strengths, including disciplinary placement, and make informed decisions about the likelihood of institutional support. For instance, if the press has authors who work at universities that have been known to support OA membership models in the past – such as Knowledge Unlatched, the Open Library of Humanities, arXiv, Subscribe to Open – then this may give confidence in that institution's support. Creating an initial spreadsheet of authorial affiliations of the Press's backlist and correlating these with institutions known to support OA initiatives may provide a benchmark of potential reach.

Tax Implications

While this document cannot dispense and does not constitute formal accountancy or legal advice with respect to taxation, there are several considerations to bear in mind:

- The United Kingdom's HMRC (the formal tax body) [previously advised the Open Library of Humanities](#) (while the UK was still a member of the EU) that membership schemes with no direct benefit to the supporting organization (library) were exempt from VAT because there was no 'supply'.
- However, because Opening the Future provides subscription access to books, a supply does occur in this model.
- But the supply of e-books is a [zero-rated activity for VAT purposes](#).

It is our belief, therefore, that Opening the Future should be treated as a zero-rated supply activity in regions that charge VAT. Supply of digital goods takes place in the country of the consumer. Hence, if you meet the VAT threshold in the country of supply, you may need to register and account for VAT, although you can charge a zero-rate.

Organizational Partnerships

Delivering a worldwide membership programme requires significant resources, which can be ameliorated by working with trusted partners. Here we list the partnerships that we developed for Opening the Future, their role in the delivery, pricing, and contact details.

Billing and Sales Partnerships

Jisc Collections

Jisc Collections works on behalf of Jisc members and customers in the United Kingdom, to negotiate and license the high-quality digital content agreements needed to support academic research, teaching and learning. Its strategic groups set the direction of national-level negotiations.²

Jisc Collections is the official intermediary for most content made available to UK libraries. Many UK libraries expect to be able to sign up through Jisc Collections. Jisc Collections have a template license developed in partnership with COPIM that can be used quickly to establish new Opening the Future programmes. Jisc Collections levy a transaction fee to publishers but do not otherwise take a cut. Jisc Collections is instead funded by its library member base.

Contact: Caroline Mackay, Licensing manager (caroline.mackay@jisc.ac.uk)

Knowledge Unlatched

Knowledge Unlatched was originally a consortial model for open access to monographs, in which many libraries paid a small amount in order to ‘unlatch’ titles.³ Over time, it has transitioned into becoming a sales agent for open access initiatives and is now owned by Wiley. Its vision ‘is a sustainable market where scholarly books and journals are freely accessible for each and every reader around the world’. Knowledge Unlatched can be a useful sales agent for European regions in particular. They take a percentage fee per transaction.

Contact: Catherine Anderson, Head of Sales (catherine@knowledgeunlatched.org)

LYRASIS

LYRASIS is a library consortium that catalyzes and enables equitable access to the world’s knowledge and cultural heritage. LYRASIS helps its members succeed by working with them to identify their needs, issues and challenges and by providing products, services and learning

2 Jisc Collections, ‘About Jisc Collections’, *Jisc*, 2021 <<https://www.jisc.ac.uk/jisc-collections>> [accessed 3 January 2022].

3 Frances Pinter and Lucy Montgomery, ‘Knowledge Unlatched: Toward an Open and Networked Future for Academic Publishing’, in *Accentuate the Positive: Charleston Conference Proceedings, 2012*, ed. by L. H. Hinds, K. P. Strauch, and B. R. Bernhardt (presented at the Annual Charleston Library Conference, United States of America: Purdue University Press, 2013), pp. 386–91 <<http://docs.lib.purdue.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1387&context=charleston>> [accessed 14 July 2020]; Frances Pinter and Christopher Kenneally, ‘Publishing Pioneer Seeks Knowledge Unlatched’, 2013 <<http://beyondthebookcast.com/transcripts/publishing-pioneer-seeks-knowledge-unlatched/>>; Lucy Montgomery and others, ‘Pilot Proof of Concept Progress Summary’ (Knowledge Unlatched, 2014) <http://collections.knowledgeunlatched.org/wp-content/uploads/2013/09/KU_Pilot_Progress_Summary_Report.pdf> [accessed 25 May 2014].

experiences to address them. LYRASIS helps its members succeed by providing leadership in and opportunities for innovation and sustainability and facilitating their pursuit of a preferred future.⁴

LYRASIS has long been a supporter of membership-based open access models in North America. Through their Open Access Community Investment Program (OACIP), LYRASIS has a broad marketing reach for open-access initiatives. LYRASIS is also usually already setup as a supplier in many North American institutional systems, thereby substantially lessening the overhead of payment processing for most presses.

LYRASIS charge a percentage transaction fee, which can be included in the financial modelling tool.

Contact: Sharla Lair, Senior Strategist, Open Access & Scholarly Communication Initiatives (sharla.lair@lyrasis.org)

Open Book Collective

The Open Book Collective is a group of OA publishers, publishing service providers and research libraries who work together through an online platform to sustain an equitable infrastructure for OA Books. On the OBC platform, a forthcoming output of the COPIM project, libraries can easily support a diversity of publishers committed to promoting co-operation and communal values in a ‘one-stop shop’ environment.

Delivery Partnerships

OAPEN

OAPEN promotes and supports the transition to open access for academic books by providing open infrastructure services to stakeholders in scholarly communication. We work with publishers to build a quality-controlled collection of open access books and provide services for publishers, libraries, and research funders in the areas of hosting, deposit, quality assurance, dissemination, and digital preservation.⁵

We deposit all books published openly through the Opening the Future scheme in OAPEN to enhance discoverability and use of the open content.

Contact: Tom Mosterd, Community Manager, DOAB / OAPEN (t.mosterd@oapen.org)

Project MUSE

Project MUSE is a leading provider of digital humanities and social science content for the scholarly community around the world.

For more than 25 years, Project MUSE has been the trusted and reliable source of complete, full-text versions of scholarly journals from many of the world's leading universities and scholarly societies. Currently, Project MUSE has over 700 journals from 125 publishers and offers nearly

4 LYRASIS, ‘Mission and Strategic Plan’, 2021 <<https://www.lyrasis.org/about/Pages/Strategic-Plan.aspx>> [accessed 3 January 2022].

5 OAPEN, ‘Online Library and Publication Platform’, 2021 <<https://oapen.org/>> [accessed 3 January 2022].

70,000 books from more than 140 presses. All books are fully integrated with Project MUSE's scholarly journal content, with collection and single title purchasing, subscription, OA books/MUSE Open and evidence-based acquisition models available.⁶

Project MUSE is used, in *Opening the Future*, to deliver subscription and OA book content. Project MUSE offers robust metadata provision to participating libraries, many of whom are already using the platform.

Of particular note, Project MUSE offers the requisite access control for the subscription portions of *Opening the Future*, thereby avoiding the need for presses to implement their own access control measures (see below on Technical Infrastructure).

Contact: Nicole Kendzejeski, Associate Director (MUSE@jh.edu)

Thoth

Thoth is an Open Dissemination System for Open Access books. It consists of:

- A GraphQL API, implementing a data model specifically designed for OA books
- A REST API to export metadata in formats like ONIX, MARC, etc.
- A WebAssembly GUI to manage metadata records.

Presses who require a metadata management system can use Thoth to integrate with Open Book Collective.

Contact: <https://thoth.pub>

⁶ Project MUSE, 'The MUSE Story', 2021 <<http://about.muse.jhu.edu/about/story/>> [accessed 3 January 2022].

Marketing and Outreach

Marketing and outreach are the most crucial but also most frequently overlooked activities in the implementation of open-access business models. While there is a popular wisdom that claims that ‘if you build it, they will come’, this does not straightforwardly appear to be the case. Implementing a new model such as Opening the Future requires a rigorous outreach, marketing, and sales framework if it is to succeed.

Outreach to Backlist Authors

Authors who have published with the press are likely to be among the keenest to ensure its future prosperity. Authors who have previously published with the press are, therefore, a key outreach point for institutional contact. That said, it is by no means guaranteed that these authors will understand the Opening the Future model or, indeed, have any knowledge of open access publishing in general. There is, for example, no guarantee that authors have heard of book processing charges and it can be a dangerous field to open.

Emails to these individuals should:

- Be addressed from a known and trusted figure, such as the acquisitions editor who worked with the author previously.
- Be specifically actionable. The email should clearly ask the author to reach out to a particular librarian, if possible with a name and contact address.
- Require as little work on the author’s part as possible. Use the below templates to attach the email that you would like the author to send to the library.
- Be personalised so as not to come across as marketing spam.
- Comply with all General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) provisions for opt-out if an author does not wish to hear any more.

Sample Email to Author

Dear X,

[insert your personal greeting]

I am writing to let you know of an innovative Open Access scheme at [insert press name]. In order for this scheme to work, and for new scholarship to be well supported, I am asking for your help with contacting your library.

Opening the Future is a membership programme for university libraries whereby they subscribe to a selection of our titles and in return we use their membership fees to publish new scholarship in Open Access format, freely available to all and with no author facing fees. You can find more details on the scheme at [insert web address].

Our books will continue to be available in print, but the pandemic has shown that not only are digital editions essential for research and teaching, but that they must also be affordable.

If you were able, please, to write to your library requesting that they sign up to support the initiative, it would be of great help. I attach a sample email you can use (copied below) and I believe the correct library contact is: [insert contact detail here]

With your - and their - help we can begin to eliminate Book Processing Charges for scholars that do not have access to research funder budgets. And we can freely disseminate new scholarship far and wide.

With many thanks for your consideration and best wishes,

[insert your name]

Sample Template Email to Library from Author

Dear [insert librarian name],

My publisher, [insert press name], has launched an innovative Open Access initiative called Opening the Future, which I would like you to consider supporting.

With annual fees of between [€£\$insert figure] and [€£\$insert figure] per institution this is a low-risk way of supporting a model that can be scaled up throughout the world of smaller university presses. [insert press name] is offering collections of excellent titles in a model similar to the 'subscribe to open' scheme which you've already seen used successfully in the journal world.

In essence [insert press name] has launched a collective subscription model that, through its membership scheme, makes library funds go further: achieving the dual objectives of increasing collections and supporting Open Access. The small annual fee would get the name of university term access to [insert number] titles, becoming perpetual access after three years; the membership revenue is used exclusively to publish new OA monographs.

The initiative has the support of COPIIM which is a reputable and well-funded driver of Open Access for monographs, dedicated to moving away from unaffordable BPCs and spreading costs more equitably.

There are further details on the Opening the Future website and signing up takes only a few minutes through a simple form at [insert signup URL]. I would encourage you to consider membership and feel free to contact the press for further details.

With many thanks for your consideration and with apologies if I have not addressed this email to exactly the right library colleague - I would be grateful if you could pass this on,

Name of author

Outreach to Frontlist Authors

The degree of enthusiasm for open access varies hugely between authors. Nonetheless, frontlist authors who are convinced of the merits of OA make for powerful allies. Writing to authors in this

category is particularly efficacious, when a work is in press or under contract, as they will often be keen to help the press to thrive.

Many of the same principles apply as in the above outreach to backlist authors, except that the relationship here is likely to be warmer and more active. The key is to do as much work on behalf of the academic as possible so that it is easy for them to write to their librarian.

Outreach to Open Access or Scholarly Communications Librarians

Open access librarians are often extremely savvy and well versed in new models for open access. Given the affordability of Opening the Future and the fact that scholarly communications budgets have been cut back in recent days, this initiative offers a powerful and affordable way for institutions to signal their support for open-access books, even when they do not have a great deal of available funding.

One potential point of confusion for this group is that they may misconstrue Opening the Future as a read-and-publish or transformative agreement. That is, they may erroneously believe that they are paying for *their authors* to publish openly with the press. Communication with librarians in this group must stress the novelty of the approach and that the aim is to reach the entire frontlist becoming OA, thereby avoiding the need for hybrid interim measures.

Key elements of this outreach include:

- Stressing the affordability of the initiative, with particular reference comparison to APCs.
- Emphasizing the need to avoid Book Processing Charges.
- Tying the request to authors from the institution without implying that this is a transformative agreement (i.e. showing that authors from the institution are publishing with the press).
- Tying the request to subject-specific readership/usages (e.g. are there textbooks set on courses at the university that are published by the press?)
- Personalisation so as not to come across as marketing spam.
- Complying with all General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) provisions for opt-out if a librarian does not wish to hear any more.

Outreach to Acquisitions/Collection Librarians and Using Worldcat Data

One of the core goals of the Opening the Future model is to shift from a bifurcated environment where acquisitions budgets are used to buy books, while scholarly communications budgets are used to fund OA, into a more holistic environment in which all acquisitions expenditure contributes to making content open for all.

When selling the Opening the Future model to acquisitions librarians, the focus should be on the unique content that is delivered to each participating library (the backlist). Institutions in this situation will also usually focus on a teaching need for the title or whether faculty have requested a purchase, which can be challenging to demonstrate. Demand-driven acquisition paradigms have also instilled a false belief in the sustainability of on-demand access.

Various data sources, such as Worldcat, can help to make the case to acquisitions librarians, although the data can be read in different ways by different institutions. For instance, if Worldcat data indicate that a library has previously purchased every title from a press, some libraries will see this as a good indication that they should join the Opening the Future model as it represents a cheaper way to acquire all new books. Others, though, may question why they should subscribe when they already have all the titles. Hence, data are never neutral and require contextualisation for each library.

Outreach to Library Consortia

Approaching library consortia can be a powerful way to generate multi-site signups and quickly gain many members. The recent MIT Press report indicated substantial success working with large groups of libraries.⁷

That said, there are a number of aspects to bear in mind with consortial groups:

- Consortial groupings can be slow in their decision making. There are often multiple layers of committees and budgets can be set up to 12 months in advance. Hence, while the rewards can be great, the lead time for consortial participation can be lengthy.
- Consortial groups are more likely to respond to larger presses with more substantial asks. There is almost a sense that below a certain threshold, it is not worth the time/participation of the big groups.
- Consortia can sometimes be distant from the purchasing process. Speaking directly on the ground with individual acquisitions and scholarly communications librarians can often yield more immediate direct results, although the rewards of landing a large-scale consortial group is key.
- Some library systems act as mini-consortia. The California Digital Library (CDL), for instance, acts on behalf of the California system and is an extremely important player in the US market. Nine libraries of the CDL group are subscribing members of Opening the Future at both Liverpool University Press and CEU Press.
- Some consortia have an extraordinarily large reach. The Center for Research Libraries (CRL) in the US is a powerful ally who has already endorsed the Opening the Future model at the Central European University Press.
- Some libraries are members of multiple consortial groups. Avoiding overlap in pricing calculations and factoring this in during growth predictions is important.

Press Releases about New Signups

The most effective marketing strategies present potential customers with multiple engagement opportunities. Because of the way that the timescales work in Opening the Future, there are many opportunities to bring the scheme to the attention of libraries.

These points include:

- Launch of the scheme/model
- Every time a library signs up (a press release with a quote from the library in question gives the library the opportunity to signal their support for open publication practices and also allows you to express gratitude in public for the signup)

⁷ Raym Crow, 'MIT Press Open Monograph Model (Direct to Open)' (Chain Bridge Group and the MIT Press, 2022).

- Reaching the revenue threshold for the next book to become open access
- Deciding which next new title will be open access (i.e. declaring the intent for a book to be published openly)
- The publication of an open-access title

Press releases that feature books and authors should be illustrated and eye catching. When launching these announcements via a social media presence, you should ‘tag’ the associated individuals – whether that is a library or an author – to ensure the broadest spread of material.

All press releases should clearly indicate how libraries can support the model, with as few clicks as possible.

Conferences and Events

Examples of conferences at which it might be prudent to market the scheme are:

- • Advancing Research Communication and Scholarship (ARCS) Conference
- • ALA Annual meeting
- • ALA Midwinter meeting
- • ALPSP conference
- • American Historical Association
- • American Theological Library Association (ATLA)
- • Annual Library Leadership Institute (ALLI) conference
- • Asian Conference on Literature and Librarianship (LIBRASIA) conference
- • Asian Digital Library Conference (ADLC)
- • Association of Asian Studies
- • Association of College & Research Libraries (ACRL) conference(s).
- • AUPresses Annual Meeting
- • Australian Library and Information Association (ALIA) Information Online conference.
- • Berlin Open Access Conference
- • Canadian Association of Research Libraries
- • Canadian Library Association (CLA) conference.
- • Charleston Conference (also Preconference)
- • Chartered Institute of Library and Information Professionals (CILIP) conference
- • CNI / Jisc library leaders conference
- • Conference of Directors of National Libraries of Asia and Oceania (CDNLAO)
- • Congress of Southeast Asian Librarians (CONSAL)
- • DCDC (RLUK, National Archives & Jisc)
- • Electronic Resources and Libraries Conference (EL&R)
- • Emerging Technologies in Academic Libraries (EmTAcL) conference.
- • FORCE
- • Frankfurt Book Fair
- • Geneva Workshop on Innovations in Scholarly Communication
- • ICOLC
- • IFLA / WLIC International Federation of Library Associations
- • Information Science in an Age of Change (ISAC) conference
- • International Coalition of Library Consortia (ICOLC).
- • International Conference on Asia-Pacific Digital Libraries (ICADL)
- • Joint Conference on Digital Libraries (JCDL)

- • Joint University Librarians Advisory Committee (JULAC) conference
- • LIBER - Association of European Research Libraries
- • Library Association of Singapore (LAS) Libraries for Tomorrow conference
- • Library Collective aka LibCon
- • Library Publishing Forum
- • London Book Fair
- • Modern Language Association
- • Munin Conference
- • MUSE Meets conference
- • Music Library Association/Theatre Library Association Joint Meeting
- • National Acquisitions Group (NAG)
- • NISO Plus
- • North American Serials Interest Group (NASIG)
- • North Carolina Serials Conference
- • OA Tage/Open Access Days (Germany)
- • OASPA conference
- • Ontario Library Association OLA Super Conference
- • Open Education Conference
- • Open Science Fair
- • Researcher 2 Reader (R2R)
- • RLUK
- • SCONUL - UK Society of College, National and University Libraries conference
- • Society for Scholarly Publishing (SSP)
- • The Higher Education Technology Agenda (THETA)
- • UKSG
- • WHEF conference

Signup Workflow

Despite its seeming simplicity, the workflow for Opening the Future is relatively complex, with multiple actors involved at different times. Coordination between different parties requires care and a technological infrastructure that can handle the effort.

The workflow has to handle the following core activities:

- Library sign up
- Payment processing
- Access control management
- Library cancellation

Process Diagram

Figure 2: The workflow for a generic/recommended Opening the Future programme

Actors and Actions

Actors	Action	Notes
Library	Completes form on website	Triggers email alerts to correct contacts at the Press and intermediaries
Jisc Collections, Knowledge Unlatched, LYRASIS, Press	Depending on the region, Jisc Collections, LYRASIS, Knowledge Unlatched or the Press itself must process the signup. In the case of Jisc Collections, the Library may also have to complete a signup on Jisc's system instead.	If a library signs up through Jisc Collections's independent catalogue platform, it may be necessary to duplicate the signup data into the Press's own CRM system and OtF site.
Jisc Collections, Knowledge Unlatched, LYRASIS, Press, Project MUSE, Other Platform	The Press or intermediary (Jisc Collections, Knowledge Unlatched, LYRASIS) informs the platform provider (Project MUSE as example) that access should be granted to the signup institution.	By default we recommend enabling access before payment is received and retracting it if not received within 3 months.
Jisc Collections, Knowledge Unlatched, LYRASIS, Press	Issue invoice to Library.	
Press	Send welcome email to Library.	This welcome email is an opportunity to thank the library and should include: Details of access to subscription packages A proposed announcement of the Library's signup (see under Marketing and Outreach)
Library	Cancellation	If a library cancels within the three year window, access should be revoked.

Delivery of Subscription Content

A core part of the Opening the Future model is the delivery of subscription content to participating libraries. This requires consideration of:

- The coherence of the subscription packages. It is vital that the collections of titles exhibit both academic and commercial appeal.
- The conditions of access. It is important that the content is hosted on a reputable platform that delivers appropriate metadata in standards-compliant formats and that the content is indexed in order to appear in library discoverability services. Some platform providers, such as Project MUSE, can help to fulfil these criteria.
- The licensing. See below on SERU for the easiest path towards licensing of subscription content.

In addition, there are a number of ‘gotchas’ that must be considered for the delivery of subscription content.

Fixed Packages Should Not Change

While it is tempting to believe that packages can be reconfigured at will, the ability to deliver custom packages is beholden to the restrictions of external suppliers. For instance, ensuring consistent metadata is delivered to Project MUSE means that once a package has been setup by the remote supplier, it should be fixed permanently. This also allows libraries to ensure that once they have access to a package, it is never withdrawn, unless they cancel.

Licensing: Use SERU Where Possible

While some institutions will require specific licenses, using the Shared E-Resource Understanding (SERU) eliminates much legal wrangling and overhead around licensing while working in a good faith capacity.⁸

As the NISO document on SERU describes itself:

SERU embodies a desire by publishers and libraries for a cooperative and collaborative relationship that recognizes that the provision of timely, high-quality materials and their protection is in the mutual interests of all parties.

SERU offers providers (such as publishers) and acquiring institutions (such as libraries) the opportunity to save both the time and the costs associated with a negotiated and signed license agreement by agreeing to operate within a framework of shared understanding and good faith. The statements below provide a set of common understandings for providers and acquiring institutions to reference as an alternative to a formal license when conducting business.

Neither the statements of understanding nor this document constitute a license agreement. Because SERU is not a license, legal terms (such as jurisdiction, warranties, and liabilities) are not used. Rather, the SERU statements describe a set of commonly agreed-upon expectations for using and providing electronic resources. While licenses are appropriate in many situations, SERU offers an alternative when both the acquiring institution and the provider are satisfied with this approach.⁹

8 NISO, ‘Shared E-Resource Understanding (SERU)’, 2015 <<http://www.niso.org/standards-committees/seru>> [accessed 4 January 2022].

9 NISO SERU Standing Committee, ‘NISO RP-7-2012, SERU: A Shared Electronic Resource Understanding’, 2012, 11.

In cases where a formal license is required, the Press must take its own legal advice as to the suitability of any particular clause. However, we recommend that any license provides the following clauses:

- Term access for the first three years;
- Perpetual access after three years' of subscription;
- An open-access, Creative Commons license for front-list open-access content released under the scheme.

Digital Preservation and Perpetual Access

Depending on the specific delivery platform, it may be appropriate to deposit books in third-party platforms, held in trust in case of future Press insolvency. 'Perpetual access' as promised by this programme should also mean perpetual access beyond the lifespan of a press. By using robust, third-party digital preservation systems, presses can provide a higher level of guaranteed availability to libraries.

Delivery of OA Content

Selection Procedures and Timescale

It is imperative that the selection process for open-access books be transparent and trustworthy. Libraries fear that publishers will select books for the open-access route that they believe will not sell, thereby implicitly devaluing open access.

We recommend that Opening the Future presses adopt a strict chronological hierarchy for the selection of the next open-access monograph. In other words, at the moment when sufficient funds have accumulated to make another book open access, the book that is next scheduled for publication in the current production schedule, but which hasn't yet been announced as OA vs. non-OA should be the chosen volume.

Icons by FlatIcon.com

Figure 3: As more members join, frontlist books can gradually be published OA

If multiple books are on the same production schedule, the Press has latitude to select which book will be OA, but we would urge transparency around this process and for the Press to issue a justificatory statement of the title's worth in such instances.

All new frontlist titles therefore could be first planned as traditionally-sold 'closed' books and as soon as the press has accrued enough library support to fund a book, the metadata should be changed before any sales are made. The distributors should then move the book to an OA status. This should happen well before the book is published.

This process, in which titles are selected prior to being sent to any third-party intermediaries, means that there is a long lead time for Opening the Future presses, before a book is made OA. However, by doing so, we completely avoid any allegations of double dipping through the provision of misleading data about title availability.

Technical Infrastructures

Two technical infrastructures exist, or will shortly exist, that can support the Opening the Future model. The first is the 'signup' system developed by the COPIM project and Birkbeck's Centre for Technology and Publishing. The second is the Open Book Collective platform developed by COPIM.

‘Signup’ Infrastructure

For those who wish to run their own infrastructure, a signup platform is available at the Github repository of the Birkbeck Centre for Technology and Publishing. The platform is written in Django/python and is available under the GNU Affero General Public License v3.0.

Features of this platform include:

- CMS system
- Ability to collect signup data
- Access control management system
- Multi-tenant hosting (more than one press per install)
- News and updates system
- Per user and per role access control

Running the signup infrastructure requires an independent web host capable of serving wsgi applications in python. The overheads of running this system locally should be matched to the Press’s in-house technical capacity. As always, the cost of free software must be measured in the time that it takes for an in-house individual to maintain a site vs. the cost of externalising/outsourcing such provision.

URL: <https://github.com/BirkbeckCTP/signup>

Open Book Collective

‘Open Book Collective’ (OBC) is a platform and intermediary organisation that allows open-access academic publishers and infrastructure providers (‘initiatives’) to promote their publishing activities and to sell and manage their funding schemes.

When launched, Open Book Collective will allow publishers to specify the data that they wish to collect and also to present Opening the Future-style initiatives on a central platform for open-access book funding models.

Open Book Collective features advanced integration with the Thoth metadata system, allowing libraries to see links to their own institutions.

Open Book Collective, when it launches, will be found at <https://www.openbookcollective.org>

Appendix A: Jisc Collections Licensing Template

See DOI [10.5281/zenodo.7003979](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7003979) for a link to this appendix MS Word document.

Appendix B: Financial Modelling Spreadsheet

See DOI [10.5281/zenodo.7003979](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7003979) for a link to this appendix MS Excel document.

Appendix C: Frequently Asked Questions

This section contains answers to the most frequently asked questions that we encountered in deploying Opening the Future. These FAQs can be used in response to queries about the model or simply to answer these questions if you have them yourself. The numbers in these FAQ responses pertain to the model at the Central European University Press's implementation of Opening the Future.

Why OA and Why Now?

The Covid-19 pandemic has shown that open access in scholarly communications is the optimal solution in a time of severe societal restriction. It seems clear that there is an opportunity to reassess how academic books can reach the world. Even without the context of Covid-19, open access is a benefit to scholars and readers alike - the following list of positive benefits is taken from the OAPEN OA Books Toolkit:

- Increased readership, usage and citation
- Wider and more diverse audiences
- Real-world impact and public engagement
- Quicker and more lasting impact
- More possibilities for readers to engage with and improve research
- Greater author control
- Compliance with funder mandates

During the first phase of Covid 19 many university and commercial publishers made their content open to the world as they rushed to assist students and researchers to gain access to content while libraries were closed. Over the months of mid-March until the end June 2020 CEU Press made 279 titles open to anyone with access to the Internet. Through the Project MUSE platform downloads exceeded 350,000 in 129 countries for books that under the closed model would have sold a couple of hundred copies in hardback. Growth in ebook usage was dramatic.

Why now when library budgets are under so much pressure?

The Covid pandemic has at once exposed how vital open access is to the future of scholarly communications while also ripping the heart out of the library budgets that can make that transition possible. Opening the Future is designed to be affordable to yield excellent value per book. At an average projected cost of €16.00 per backlist title, €32.00 per frontlist title, or €10.67 per book on aggregate. Whichever way you look at it, Opening the Future provides a good return on library investment.

What happens if a frontlist title has access to other funding as as BPC from a research grant?

Our policy is to first seek funding from other sources and only if that is not available (which it is still not in most cases) would we apply the funds raised from this project to make books open.

Can this model scale for use by other publishers without inundating libraries with lots of tiny deals?

We hope that with the documented success of Opening the Future we will have a model that could lead to the widespread transition of university presses worldwide to OA. COPIM is also working on

producing something like a 'shopping mall' to facilitate support and enable library choice. Called the 'Open Book Collective' this non-profit platform will allow open-access academic publishers and infrastructure providers to promote their publishing activities, manage and sell their funding schemes to libraries.

Why would a research funder be interested in this programme and how can they get involved?

Open access is of clear benefit to research funders, who can then ensure the maximum public impact of the work that they fund. Funders have, in the past, supported other consortial membership schemes in the journal space and we hope that this will translate to books as we seek a more open future.

What is the goal of this model?

Nothing less than to show a route to sustainable OA for the foundational publications of the Humanities and Social Sciences.

How can revenue targets be reached? And what happens if and when they are reached?

Revenue targets can be reached as more libraries join up. Once achieved we will reduce the membership fees, or with members' consent, make more books open access.

Is this program open to library consortia deals?

Since success in opening all books depends on the income this will be considered but can reflect only the savings in administration and marketing costs. Please contact us to discuss:

When will you make books open access?

As soon as we have the revenue, the next book to be published will be OA, though with a gap of a few months to ensure the metadata that goes out about its OA status overrides any pre-publication publicity about the book. In this way we hope to avoid libraries buying books because their OA status was announced too late.

Is this like a 'Read and Publish' deal, but for books?

No, the model is not based on the support of individual titles. If anything it's more like a 'Subscribe to Open' offer. Participating libraries get unlimited access to curated selections of backlist eBooks at a much cheaper price than buying them in print one at a time. The subscription fees are then used to 'unlock' new OA books. It's that simple. There are no BPCs charged, and authors at participating libraries do not get 'preferential' or 'discounted' publishing deals: OA books are chosen on merit, through the normal editorial proposal process and are peer reviewed. The cost of producing OA books is paid for by the collected library subscription fees: so the more libraries sign up, the more OA books can be published.

What do subscribing members get for their money?

Members receive access to packages of 50 titles from CEU Press's extensive backlist on Central and East Europe and the former Soviet Union - the history of the region dating back to the middle ages, communism and transitions to democracy. There are four packages to choose from but each

will contain titles proven by recent download figures to be popular and current according to data from Project MUSE. One package has been curated by an independent panel of subject expert library colleagues. While not a pick and mix model entirely there is sufficient choice for libraries to select what meets their collection and reader requirements best.

How much do members pay per year?

Library and institutional members are banded according to their size, as recognised by LYRASIS and Jisc. Based on this, the structure at Central European Press, as an example, is:

- €1200 high tier, per year (approx \$1,425 USD / £1,000 GBP)
-
- €800 medium tier, per year (approx \$950 USD / £700 GBP)
-
- €350 lower tier, per year (approx \$425 USD / £300 GBP)

Membership is for a minimum of three years.

Member libraries and institutions will have unlimited concurrent/simultaneous access to all titles in the package they've subscribed to during the term of their three year membership. They will be entitled to perpetual access to that package at the end of their three year membership. You may sign up for access to a separate package at any time - this membership and package access will also be for a minimum of three years.

Will member libraries/institutions have unlimited access to the books in the subscription packages? And what happens at the end of three years?

Member libraries and institutions will have unlimited concurrent/simultaneous access to all titles in the package they've subscribed to during the term of their three year membership. They will be entitled to perpetual access to that package at the end of their three year membership.

What will be the format of the book subscription package and what services will be available to members?

The books in the subscription packages are hosted on Project MUSE in their standard DRM-free, unlimited-use model for ebooks. Content is delivered in chapter-based PDF format. Full-text searching is available across all books and within individual titles. MUSE supports authentication via IP, Shibboleth, and referring URL. Participating libraries will be able to make use of MUSE's Library Dashboard to access MARC records and KBART files customised to their holdings, and to retrieve COUNTER 5-compliant usage statistics.

MUSE collaborates with all major library discovery vendors and will ensure the packages are set up as collections to be activated in all pertinent discovery services. Books on the MUSE platform are preserved through participation in PORTICO's E-Book Preservation service.

Project MUSE is committed to the accessibility of content and complies with the Americans with Disabilities Act (ADA), in a manner consistent with the Web Accessibility Initiative Web Content Accessibility Guidelines 2.1 AA.

What if I want access to more than one package?

You can sign up to as many packages as you like - simply fill in the form for each package you want access to, or you can always contact us if you want to discuss it first.

If a library doesn't have a discretionary OA budget, can they still participate?

You can sign up to as many packages as you like - simply fill in the form for each package you want access to, or you can always contact us if you want to discuss it first:

Yes, absolutely. Funds from any budget are accepted. In fact, we are hoping that as libraries see this to be a cheaper way of building collections they will pay for this type of offer through their acquisitions budgets.

How have the packages been composed?

The four packages of 50 titles each have been assembled in different ways. The first covers History and is primarily made up of the most accessed titles on the Project MUSE platform. The second is Political Science, again selected by their ranking on Project MUSE. The third, selected by the editors at CEU Press, is wider in subject areas and includes gems in literature, such as the Classics list, gender studies, Roma, labour, public health, nationalities, Jewish studies, human rights and more. The fourth is a package made up of titles selected from the other three packages, by a small independent panel of librarians.

Will there be any DRM restrictions on the backlist?

No, all backlist package titles that you are subscribed to will be DRM-free and accessible by multiple users simultaneously.

How will the OA books be made available?

The new titles funded by the program to be published open access will be hosted on Project MUSE, and OAPEN and ORL. OA books will be available in PDF format with CC BY NC ND licences. Project MUSE supports open access books with MARC records, KBART files, and metadata sharing with major library vendors, to ensure that OA content is widely discoverable through library systems. The books will also be listed in DOAB.

Will CEU Press also sell print copies of the OA books? If so, where does the money from these sales go?

Yes. All OA titles will be available to purchase in print form. The revenue that we need to make books OA is already reduced by the amount that we hope to raise from continuing print sales. Print books can be bought through the normal channels.

I already own the backlist titles/don't need access to the books but would still like to support the OA programme. Can I do this?

Yes. We appreciate that some institutions may not wish to sign up to a book package, or may not be able to. However they might still want to support, and help to fund, the Open Access monographs that CEU Press will be publishing. For these institutions we have created an 'OA Supporter

Membership'. It is simple and quick to join: just fill in the sign up form with the appropriate details and we'll do the rest. No further action is required from you once we have processed the payment.

Why do we use sales agents and other organisations for outreach?

Transitioning to Open Access is hard and we're in the midst of a transition where we need to accommodate the needs of libraries with a model that is new. We understand that libraries often need to go through extensive deliberations amongst their own stakeholders to see if it is worth investing in our particular offer. As a small press we do not have the resources to talk to every librarian, so we rely on the non-profit membership organization LYRASIS in North America who are already communicating with librarians every day, and sales agents like Knowledge Unlatched elsewhere in the world.

Bibliography

- Crow, Raym, 'MIT Press Open Monograph Model (Direct to Open)' (Chain Bridge Group and the MIT Press, 2022)
- Jisc Collections, 'About Jisc Collections', *Jisc*, 2021 <<https://www.jisc.ac.uk/jisc-collections>> [accessed 3 January 2022]
- LYRISIS, 'Mission and Strategic Plan', 2021 <<https://www.lyrasis.org/about/Pages/Strategic-Plan.aspx>> [accessed 3 January 2022]
- Montgomery, Lucy, Christina Emery, Frances Pinter, and Leon Loberman, 'Pilot Proof of Concept Progress Summary' (Knowledge Unlatched, 2014) <http://collections.knowledgeunlatched.org/wp-content/uploads/2013/09/KU_Pilot_Progress_Summary_Report.pdf> [accessed 25 May 2014]
- NISO, 'Shared E-Resource Understanding (SERU)', 2015 <<http://www.niso.org/standards-committees/seru>> [accessed 4 January 2022]
- NISO SERU Standing Committee, 'NISO RP-7-2012, SERU: A Shared Electronic Resource Understanding', 2012, 11
- OAPEN, 'Online Library and Publication Platform', 2021 <<https://oapen.org/>> [accessed 3 January 2022]
- Penier, Izabella, Martin Paul Eve, and Tom Grady, 'Revenue Models for Open Access Monographs 2020', *Community-Led Open Publication Infrastructures for Monographs*, 2020 <<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4011836>>
- Pinter, Frances, and Christopher Kenneally, 'Publishing Pioneer Seeks Knowledge Unlatched', 2013 <<http://beyondthebookcast.com/transcripts/publishing-pioneer-seeks-knowledge-unlatched/>>
- Pinter, Frances, and Lucy Montgomery, 'Knowledge Unlatched: Toward an Open and Networked Future for Academic Publishing', in *Accentuate the Positive: Charleston Conference Proceedings, 2012*, ed. by L. H. Hinds, K. P. Strauch, and B. R. Bernhardt (presented at the Annual Charleston Library Conference, United States of America: Purdue University Press, 2013), pp. 386–91 <<http://docs.lib.purdue.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1387&context=charleston>> [accessed 14 July 2020]
- Project MUSE, 'The MUSE Story', 2021 <<http://about.muse.jhu.edu/about/story/>> [accessed 3 January 2022]